

in the butachlor-treated plots until 15 days after crop emergence. However, there was a significant reduction (42.9%, see table) in the stand count of BR6 rice. The cultivar seemed to be very much susceptible to butachlor. The yields of the butachlor-treated plots were significantly lower than those of

the plots hand weeded three times.

Weed counts and weights taken at 4 weeks after transplanting of the second rice crop showed no significant difference among the treatments. That indicates that butachlor had no residual effect on the weed growth of the second crop.

Major weeds in both rice crops were *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link, *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Cyperus iria* L., and *Fimbristylis littoralis* Gaud.

Further study of butachlor at different rates of application and on different cultivars of dry-seeded rice seems essential. ■

Studies on the chemical control of weeds in dry-seeded wetland rice

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The effectiveness of certain herbicides was assessed in a field experiment during samba (Aug-Dec) with the rice variety ADT31. The test herbicides were propanil, butachlor, and 2,4-D. The herbicides were sprayed once 10 days after sowing. The first weeding was done 30 days after sowing and the second weeding, 45 days after sowing. Each time the monocot and dicot weeds were sorted separately, and their weights recorded by plot. The consolidated wet weights of monocot and dicot weeds were analyzed statistically. The grain

and straw yield of rice also were recorded.

The treatment differences with regard to control of both monocot and dicot weeds were statistically significant. Among the herbicides tested 2,4-D and propanil were superior in controlling monocot weeds; propanil and butachlor were effective in controlling dicot weeds

(see table). The treatment differences with respect to grain yield were also statistically significant. Butachlor and propanil were equally significantly superior to 2,4-D and the hand-weeded check. Butachlor and propanil increased yield by 17.9 and 15.7%, respectively, over the control; 2,4-D increased it by 6.4% over the hand-weeded check. ■

Effectiveness of certain herbicides in the control of weeds for dry-seeded wetland rice.

Herbicide	Rate (kg ai/ ha)	Mean wt (g/m ²)		Grain yield (t/ha)	Percent increase over control
		Monocot	Dicot		
2,4-D	5 kg in 250 liters water	114.60	221.45	2.78	6.40
Propanil	7.5 liters in 250 liters water	155.75	124.95	3.02	15.79
Butachlor	5 liters in 250 liters water	249.20	143.00	3.08	17.90
Control (hand weeding)		323.50	366.50	2.61	-
SE		41.34	48.97	.103	
CD		42.78	150.88	.317	

Light requirements for growth of some perennial paddy weeds

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Knowing the light requirements of weeds is important in determining weed damage to crops and in developing methods of ecological control. We examined the growth response of four major perennial paddy weeds in Japan — *Sagittaria pygmaea*, *S. trifolia*, *Cyperus serotinus*, and *Eleocharis kuroguwai* — to reduced light (60, 45, 22, and 9% relative sunlight) in the field. The plant number and dry weight of shoots of *S. pygmaea* per unit area greatly increased in 60% and 45% sunlight (see figure). The dry weight of shoots of *S. trifolia* also increased in 60% sunlight. But the number of plants and shoot dry weight

Effect of limitation of sunlight on the growth of some perennial paddy weeds, Japan. *70.0 g/m, **369.2 g/m², ***462.5 g/m², ****430.0 g/m². Mean solar radiation at control during the treatment period: 367.3 cal/cm² per day.

of *C. serotinus* and *E. kuroguwai* rapidly decreased with diminishing sunlight. Tuber formation of these weeds (except *S. trifolia*) decreased in such conditions.

The results suggest that the shoot growth of *S. pygmaea* and *S. trifolia* is more adapted to reduced light than that of the two sedges *C. serotinus* and *E. kuroguwai*. ■

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